

DIP4FISH

This blog is dedicated to Digital Image Processing for fluorescence in-situ hybridization and other things about the telomeres.

Monday, March 19, 2012

Genomic head to head telomeric sequences detection by one primer PCR

Introduction

Dicentric chromosomes are the signature of recombination events which may imply telomeric motifs. To observe dicentric chromosomes in senescent cells, a cell culture followed by an enrichment step is performed to get enough metaphasic cells. However metaphasic cells become difficult to get as the cell culture reaches senescence or if cells differentiate, thus most of fusions between short telomeres, when they occur, remain hidden in interphasic cells.

Telomeric fusions can generate head to head TTAGGG motifs as:

Such kind of sequence is known in the human genome at the 2q13-q14 locus (*Ijdo et al.*).

>gi|180516|gb|M73018.1|HUMCHR2A Human ancestral telomeric fusion DNA sequence
GTGCCCGGCGCCACGAGGGCGCTGGCGACCACTGTAAGCAAGAGAGCCCTGCGCCTCTCTGCGCCTGCG

CGGCCGGGCCGGCCGCCCTTTGCGATGGCGGAGTTGCGTTCTCCTCAGCACAGACCCGGAGAGCACC
 GCAGGGCGACCTGCGTTGTCTCTGCACAGATTTGCGTGGTACTGCGAAGGCGGACGAGAGTTCTCCTCAG
 GTCAGACCCGGGCCGGCCGGCTAGGATACCGCGAGGCGAGCTGCGTTCTGCTCAGCACAGACCTGGGGG
 TCACCGTAAAGATGGAGCAGCATTCCCTAAGCACAGAGGTTGGGGCCACTGCCTGGCTTTGTGACAACT
 CGGGGCGCATCAACGGTGAATAAAATCTTTCCCGGTTGCAGCCGTGAATAATCAAGGTGAGAGCCAGTT
 AGAGCGGTTTCTAGTGGGAAAAAGGAAAGAAAAAGCCCTCTGAATCCTGGGCAGCGAGATTATCCAAA
 GCAAGGCGAGGGGCTGCATTGAGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGT
 GGGGTTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGTGGGGT
 CAGGGTCAGGGTTAGGGTTTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTT
 AGGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTT
 AGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAGGGTTAG
 GGTTAGCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCT
 ACCCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAAC
 ACCCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAAC
 ACCCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAAC
 CCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAAC
 CCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAAC
 CCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAAC
 CTAGCCCTAGCCCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAAC
 CCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAAC
 CCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAACCTAAC
 CAGAACGCACGTCGCGCTCGCAGTGCCTCAGCCGGGCTGACCTGAGAAGAACTGTCTCGCCTTC
 GCAATAGCCCCGAAGTCTGTGAGAGGAGAACGCAGCTCCGCCCTCGCGATGCTCTTCGGCTGTGTGCTA
 AAGAGAACGCAACTCCGCCCTCGCAAAGGCGGCCGCCGCGGAGGCGGAGAGGCGGCGGCCGCGGAG
 GCCGGAGAGGCGCGGCCGCGGGAGGCGGAGAGGCGCGGCCGCGGAGGCGGAGAGGCGCGGCCGCGG
 CGGAGGCCGAGAGGCGCGGCCGCGGGAGGCGGAGAGGCGCGGCCGCGGAGGCGCGGCCGCGG

The fusion point of this sequence is:

. . TTAGGGTTAGCTAACCTAA . .

It is the cicatrix of an ancestral chromosomal fusion occurred during karyotype evolution. As the human 2q13-q14 contains a short amount of degenerated telomeric motifs these motifs are degenerated so they cannot be detected by QFISH with (CCCTAA)₃ PNA probe (most of the time):

Possible QFISH detection of telomeric motifs at 2q13-q14 on one HSA2 homolog. Interstitial telomeric motifs are detected at the junction of euchromatin/heterochromatin on the Y chromosome. (Red: telomeric (CCCTAA)₃-PNA probe, contrast was increased after background subtraction)

Using Polymerase Chain Reaction and only one (TTAGGG)_n primer, would it be possible to detect head-to-head genomic telomeric sequences possibly resulting from chromosomal fusion ?

Detection of a genomic head-to-head telomeric sequence by PCR amplification with one (TTAGGG)_n primer (Dark Blue big arrow)

Here was investigated the possibility to detect somatic telomeric fusion occurring in senescent or SV40-transformed fibroblasts by one primer PCR amplification of head-to-head telomeric sequences. (J-P Pommier, unpublished data)

It was found that PCR products (next called G PCR products) can be produced from genomic human DNA with single TTAGGG primers. It is known that human genome DNA contains head-to-head telomeric motifs and possibly some were generated by chromosomal instability in cultured cells.

Material and method:

The cycle conditions of the first PCR assay were inspired by the paper of [Ijdo et al.](#) . As no PCR product was detected with these conditions, the stringency conditions were relaxed by decreasing the annealing temperature, without my lab-book, I cannot bring more precision on the cycling conditions.

Two kinds of assay were performed: G-PCR with (TTAGGG)_n primers (n=3 or 5) or C-PCR with (CCCTAA)_n primers (n=3 or 5) , both with 100ng of genomic DNA (high molecular weight placenta DNA, primary fibroblasts, SV40 transformed fibroblast pre-crisis/post-crisis, wild type *S. cerevisiae* genomic DNA was also tested). In a second assay, both G and C primers were used at high (100 nM?) or low (20 nM?) concentration. G3-primer and C3-primer had 5' non telomeric sequence allowing a second PCR round with a non telomeric primer.

In an assay, prior PCR, 1 microgramme of genomic DNA was digested by Hpa II (methylation sensitive) or Msp I restriction endonuclease (NEB) targeting GGCC or by another endonuclease targeting a TTAA restriction site. A 100ng aliquot was then submitted to G-PCR.

PCR products were analysed in a 2-3% agarose gel electrophoresis, stained with ethidium bromide, with a molecular weight standard in the range 200 to 2000 bp approximately (possibly molecular weight marker IV, Roche?).

Results:

Genomic DNA from placenta, primary fibroblasts, precrisis SV40 transformed fibroblasts submitted to G5-PCR (wells n°6,8,10) yield a smear like PCR product with possibly discrete bands. The same genomic DNA submitted to C5-PCR yield a smears as PCR product with no bands.

From left to right: Wells n°2, 13: molecular weight markers. Wells n°6, 8, 10: G5-PCR with (TTAGGG)₅ primer. Wells n°7, 9, 11: C5-PCR with (CCCTAA)₅ primer. Well n°12:?. The wells n°3, 4 may be some control (no primer, no genomic DNA).

More conditions were tested in the following assay:

C5-PCR or C3-PCR yield a smear as PCR product at high concentration. The PCR product becomes undetectable at low primer concentration. I performed C5-PCR or C3-PCR as a control, I didn't expect to detect a PCR product with a (CCCTAA)_n primer due to the head to head orientation of the telomeric motifs in a telomeric fusion. Queue-to-queue telomeric motifs may occur, but those PCR products are likely PCR artifacts.

More interestingly, G5-PCR and G3-PCR yield bands-like PCR products with human DNA in all conditions:

- Bands are observed with human DNA as PCR target, whereas a smear is observed with yeast DNA, indicating that the PCR product detect a specific structure in the human genome which is not present in the yeast genome.
- With the "eyes of faith" (les yeux de la foi), G5-PCR at high concentration primer, seems to distinguish postcrisis DNA (well 8, upper) from normal or precrisis DNA (wells 6,7 upper) by an relative increase of the amount of the short band. As the SV40 transformed fibroblasts reach the crisis, the frequency of dicentric chromosomes increase and become stable when an immortal clone emerge from the crisis. It is consistent with an accumulation of head-to-head telomeric motif generated by chromosomal fusion between short telomeres.

- The shortest band (~600 bp) vanishes from the PCR product as the G5 primer concentration is diminished regardless the source of DNA (primary cells, precrisis or postcrisis cells). There are possibly several ancestral HTH telomeric motifs per cell, whereas there is less than one neo HTH telomeric motif per cell (statistically around the crisis, cells have 0 or 1 dicentric chromosomes, even some cells have more). As neo HTH telomeric motifs are rare events, decreasing G5 primer would decrease PCR detection efficiency. The same for G3 primer due to thermal stability.

In the last assay the presence of palindromic sequences in potential HTH telomeric motifs was tested with G5-PCR only.

Some of them generate palindromic sequences as GGCC cut by the isoschisomers Hpa II / Msp I restriction endonucleases, or TTAA. There are 36 possible head-to-head telomeric motifs as follow:

	TTAGGG	TAGGGT	AGGGTT	GGGTTA	GGTTAG	GTTAGG
CCCTAA	TTAGGGCCCTAA	TAGGGTCCCTAA	AGGGTTCCCTAA	GGGTTACCCTAA	GGTTAGCCCTAA	GTTAGGCCCTAA
CCTAAC	TTAGGGCCTAAC	TAGGGTCCTAAC	AGGGTTCCTAAC	GGGTACCTAAC	GGTTAGCCTAAC	GTTAGGCCTAAC
CTAACC	TTAGGGCTAACC	TAGGGTCTAACC	AGGGTCTAACC	GGGTACTAACC	GGTTAGCTAACC	GTTAGGCTAACC
TAACCC	TTAGGGTAACCC	TAGGGTTAACCC	AGGGTTAACCC	GGGTATAACCC	GGTTAGTAACCC	GTTAGGTAACCC
AACCCT	TTAGGGAACCCT	TAGGGTAACCCT	AGGGTAAACCCT	GGGTTAACCCT	GGTTAGAACCCT	GTTAGGAACCCT
ACCCTA	TTAGGGACCCTA	TAGGGTACCCTA	AGGGTACCCTA	GGGTTAACCCTA	GGTTAGACCCTA	GTTAGGACCCTA

If the telomeric fusion point contains a palindromic sequence, submitting the genomic DNA to endonuclease prior G5-PCR may prevent the PCR amplification:

Endonuclease digestion of DNA may prevent G-PCR amplification.

In uncut DNA (primary fibroblasts (line 1), precrisis fibroblasts (line 6), immortalized clone (line 11)), G5-PCR produces two major bands below 1200 bp. Those bands vanished as DNA is cut with MspI (GGCC) or with an endonuclease targeting TTAA sequence (from left to right, primary cells, pre or post-crisis fibroblasts: lines 2, 4, 7, 9, 12, 13), indicating that palindromic sequences exist between inverse tandem telomeric motifs.

When genomic DNA is cut with HpaII, an endonuclease cutting GGCC motifs free of methylcytosine, the G-PCR product cannot be distinguished from the uncut DNA (lines 3, 8, 13), indicating that the cytosines are methylated in/between inverse telomeric motifs.

G5-PCR following endonuclease cut (Agarose gel + EtBr). ([well 1](#): primary fibroblast DNA (PF) uncut, [well 2](#): PF+MspI, [well 3](#): PF+HpaII, [well 4](#): PF+TTAA cut, [well 5](#): molecular weight markers (possibly :2176, 1766, 1230, 1033, 653, 517, 453 bp), [well 6](#): precrisis transformed (PT) fibroblast uncut, [well 7](#): PT+MspI, [well 8](#): PT+HpaII, [well 9](#): PT+TTAA cut, [well 10](#): mw marker(?), [well 11](#): Immortalized postcrisis fibroblast (IF) uncut, [well 12](#): IF+MspI, [well 13](#): IF+HpaII, [well 14](#): IF+TTAA cut.

Discussion:

If the aim was to detect somatic telomeric fusions associated to cellular senescence or to cellular

transformation, the G5-PCR assays failed to distinguish clearly the different cell states. The G-PCR to detect end-to-end telomeric fusion may be optimized ([PCR optimization](#)) by increasing stringency:

- by increasing annealing T°
- by decreasing elongation time
- using hot-start PCR (Taq hot-start or wax)

Prior PCR, genomic DNA could be digested by Bal31 to completely remove terminal telomeric motifs and to keep telomeric motifs belonging to potential fusion points.

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (PAGE) with P32-labelled (TTAGGG)_n primer instead of ethidium-bromide stained agarose gel to visualize PCR product, may detect somatic telomeric fusions in the range 0-600 bp. In the last example, the six last lines correspond to G-PCR products were visualized by PAGE (may be products corresponding to lines 6 to 11 in the second assay).

Real time PCR, *in-situ* PCR on nuclei could be also considered.

Six G5-PCR products (right side) in a PAGE+Ethidium Bromide staining

I was expecting that detection of somatic telomeric fusions yields short PCR products, below 500 bp. The bands in the 1Kb range, are not so short. They may correspond to head-to-head telomeric motifs flanking non telomeric sequences (containing TTAA and methyl-C GGCC motifs).

This last hypothesis could be checked by FISH. The G-PCR product could be labelled (after a second round of PCR) with Fluo-dNTP and hybridized on metaphasic chromosomes. Three FISH conditions could be set:

1. labelled G-PCR product alone: some loci should be detected.
2. labelled G-PCR product+excess of Cot1 DNA: should compete satellite DNA. Detected loci should contain non satellite sequence, possibly telomeres or unique sequences.
3. labelled G-PCR product+excess of unlabeled telomeric DNA (produced by PCR, Ijdo & al.): detected loci should not contain telomeric motifs.

Of course, G-PCR product should be insensitive to Bal-31 digestion of the genomic DNA prior PCR amplification.

Posted by dip4fish at 1:55 AM

Labels: [aging](#), [assay](#), [cancer](#), [CCCTAA](#), [dicentric chromosome](#), [interstitial telomere](#), [interstitial telomeric sequence](#), [PCR](#), [telomeric fusion](#), [TTAGGG](#)

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